

Human Resource Planning of Business Education Teachers in the 21st Century Education in Nigeria

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Abstract

The paper examined human resource planning of Business Education Teachers in the 21st century education in Nigeria. The paper identified Human resources skills, potentials, talents, and knowledge that are possessed by a person or a population which can be harnessed for quality productivity geared towards developing an economy. It anchored its theory on Knowledge Resource Strategy theory. Three major issues in Human resource planning of business education teachers were identified, which include: assessing the need for staff, satisfying the need for staff, maintaining and improving staff services. Strategic roles and operational roles were also highlighted. Functions of human resource planning in education such as staff maintenance, staff relations, staff development and job performance reward were equally x-rayed. In addition, the paper enumerated the challenges of human resource planning. It was concluded that Human resource planning in this 21st century remains a veritable means of ensuring success in the education sector. Suggestions were made, such as: the Government should, make funds available for educational sector needed for effective planning. All levels of human resources in the educational sector in Nigeria should be trained to acquire information and communication technology competencies.

Keywords: Human Resources, Human Resource Management, Planning, Business Education teachers.

Introduction

Human resources planning otherwise called, manpower planning is very crucial in establishing organization's goal. Business education teachers across schools in Nigeria require to be planned for in line with contemporary needs. Business education teachers has been identified in this paper as trained teachers who teach business subjects such as Marketing, Office Information, Accounting, Management in secondary or tertiary institutions. The concept of 21st century is in line with the planning and selection of business teachers who are able to pass business education especially in the modern, technology era. Planning of business education teachers is important as business is the bedrock of the society. Manpower planning entails the identification of goals and objectives of organization and working out ways and means of achieving them. In more simple terms, manpower planning is therefore incorporated in every man's activity economically, politically and socially. Planning is known and practiced by every race in the world. Every action

of man is an output of his thought otherwise known as strategic planning. Planning is a systematic, conscious and deliberate process of deciding ahead of time, the future course of action that a person wishes to pursue in any field of human, endeavor (Undie, Ekere & Adah, 2011).

Every planning is usually done with a view of achieving some defined objectives using available resources maximally. Human resources planning in business education can also be seen as the design of formal systems in schools to achieve quality teaching of business education subjects. Graffin (1997) as cited in Agabi (2002), defined human resource management as a set of organizational activities directed at attracting, developing and maintaining an effective workforce. Human resource management is concerned with the procurement or recruitment, staffing, welfare, maintenance, training and retraining, placement, promotion, motivation, relationship, compensation or rewards transfer and discipline of staff. It lies at the care of the efficiency of the organization. It is a basic function of management that determines the performance of staff in any organization. This simply implies that when staffs in any education system are adequately recruited, selected and supervised, inducted and adequately rewarded and provided for developed, appraised and promoted on the job, they will be committed to do the job, remain dedicated and productive in the educational system.

The essence of Taylor's assumption is that the organization should be able to derive maximum output from the activities of workers in the organization. Therefore, for the education system to succeed, the basic human resources needed must be supplied and harnessed satisfactorily. The basic resources needed for the sector are human and material resources. However, human resources are the most important in any organization after availability of capital; hence the role of the teacher and school administrator as human resource personnel to a great extent determines how well the school will meet her overall objectives and consequent development of the society (Capelli, 2000). This can simply be put as the efforts of the workers in educational organization so that educational goals are achieved. Hence human resource management in education is the process of motivating workers to maximize their performance in order to obtain maximum output starting from the utilization of people to perform duties and functions in the school (Onah, 2008). Human resources are easily recognized as the most important resource out of the resources required for the production of goods and services. Human resources are the key to rapid socio-economic development and efficient service delivery, especially in this 21st century (Onah, 2008). Without an adequate, skilled and well-motivated workforce operating within a sound human resource management programme, development in such organization will not be possible.

Every educational system at every level depends heavily on the human resources for execution of its programmes. Nwaka and Ofojebe (2010) stated that teachers are the critical resources for effective implementation and realization of the educational policies and objectives at the practical level of classroom. A manager, whether in private or public sector, who underrates the critical role and underplays the importance of people in goal achievement (Omojunwa, 2007), will not achieve maximum output. Maintaining and improving educational standards is only possible through teachers. Teachers therefore are the most indispensable entity in the school. They help to effect learning to take place. The shortage or poor management of teachers reduces the extent to which curriculum can be delivered effectively. It should be noted that the major premise of human resources management in education is that the end result of the education process will be determined by the effectiveness of the teachers who facilitate learning for self-actualization and national development especially in this 21st century.

For any organization to survive, the effective planning of human resources is very paramount. In every organization or institution, resource planning is one of the fundamental parts of the overall management of the organization. In a school setting, every operation in the system is determined by the resources provided and how they are utilized maximally to achieve organizational goals. Current happenings coupled with advances in science and technology specifies that an organization should adopt modern approaches to management in order to improve the quality of teaching and learning in this 21st century. This is so, because a direct relationship exists between the qualities of human resources in terms of quality of staff, teaching personnel and the education process which will eventually determine the instructional programmes and performance of the school.

Literature Review

Theoretical Foundation

The paper based its theory on Knowledge Resource Strategy theory by Grant 1996. Grant stated the importance of the creating, transferring and integrating the knowledge within the organization. The study is anchored on this theory because of link to knowledge base in the skill of contemporary approaches to the teaching of business education in Nigerian schools (Hesterly, 2007). Although it is difficult to imitate the firm-specific knowledge, it is not impossible. But, it is not possible to imitate the people through their capabilities, experiences, skills, and knowledge (Spender, 1996).

Human Resources Planning

Human resource planning in business education, according to Adesina in Azunwena and Uchenna (2011) is a process of preparing a set of decisions about educational enterprise in such a way that the goals and objectives of education will be sufficiently realized in the future with the available resources. Educational planning deals with how to harness the available human and materials resources to achieve educational goals. It is a continuous, process concerned with where to go and how to get there by the best possible route. Planning becomes necessary if education must be used to address the challenges of Nigerian society. Emechubie (2011) enumerated the following reasons why educational planning is necessary in every school organization. It helps management to clarify focus and research their organization development and prospects. It offers a benchmark against which actual performance can be measured and reviewed. It plays vital role in helping to avoid mistake or recognize hidden opportunities. Human resource is simply the prompt and professional use of human resource for organizational objectives. The concept of human resource utilization is similar to that of human resource management. Human resource utilization therefore focuses on using the right mix of staff with the right task or responsibility to achieve the right or expected result. Human resources focus on the availability and use of academic and non-academic staff which determines the success or failure of the educational system. However, before teachers can work towards the achievement of school objectives, they need to be trained to carry out their activities professionally. Human resources undoubtedly play the most important part in the functioning of an organization. The term “resource” or human resource signifies potentials, abilities, capabilities and skills which can be developed through continuous interaction in an organizational setting. The interactions, interrelationships, and activities performed all contribute in some way or the other to the development of human potential. Organizational productivity, growth of any educational sector, companies. And economic developments are to a large extent contingent upon the effective utilization of human capabilities. This planning is necessary in this

21st century, educational planners are to plan education in Nigeria to reflect the scope of educational planning. Here, educational planning covers the following areas: Curriculum Planning, Manpower Planning, Educational Finance Planning, Educational Statistics Planning, School Mapping and School Planning as well as educational development planning (Adiele, Obasi, & Ohia 2021). In the various stages in the growth of an organization, effective planning of human resources plays a key role. Matching the requirements of the job with the individual is important at all stages, including the recruitment procedures, in this endeavour.

Human resources planning enables business education managers to understand more clearly what they want to achieve, how to achieve it and when it can be achieved. Based on these reasons, it could be said that educational planning involves the process of identifying educational needs, the direction which education should take and how to implement the plans. To further stress the relevance of implementation of plan, UNESCO (2004) asserts that preparation of a comprehensive plan will not guarantee success but its effective implementation will. Therefore, it is necessary to plan education, implement plans and evaluate the planning process for attainment of education goals at different levels of education. Okunamiri (2003) observes that the purpose of educational planning is to ensure the systematic accomplishment of a series of activities leading towards the achievement of set objectives of educational development.

The Role of Human Resource Management Planning in Business Education

Human resource management planning has some specific roles to play in business education. These are strategic and operational roles.

- a) **Strategic Role:** Human resources are critical for effective educational functioning. Human resources were once relegated to second-class status, but its importance has grown dramatically in the last three decades. Again, its importance stems from adequately recruited, selected and supervised, inducted and adequately rewarded, provided for, properly developed, appraised and promoted on the job. This will have a corresponding effect on commitment to the job, dedication. It also represents a significant investment of the educational efforts. If managed well, human resources can be a source of competitive strength for the education. Strategically, human resources must be viewed in the same context as the financial, technological and other resources that are managed in any organization (Onah, 2008).
- b. **Operational Role:** According to Mathis and Jackson (1997) as cited in Umaah (2021). Operational activities are both tactical and administrative in nature, Griffin (1997) as cited in Agabi (2002), sees operational role from the legal perspective because some have regulated various aspects of employee-employer relations. Human resources management is therefore, interested in compliance with equal employment opportunities and observation of labour laws; examples; applicants must be oriented to the organizations, supervisors must be trained, safety problems must be resolved; wages and salaries must be administered. A wide range of activities typically associated with the day-to-day management of people as provided by laws and regulations must be performed efficiently. It is this collection of activities that has often been referred to as the personnel function, and the newer strategic focus of human resources management has not been eliminated.

Functions of Human Resources Management Planning for Business Education Teachers

Human resource management planning in education is a set of practices and methods of integrating and maintaining the teaching staff in any educational institution so that the

institution can achieve their purpose and as well as meet the goals for which they were established. It is the motivation and co-ordination of the activities and efforts of the teachers in the school in order to obtain maximum output from them and consequently achieve the goals of education optimally. The functions include the following:

- a. Staff maintenance
- b. Staff relations
- c. Staff development
- d. Procurement of staff
- e. Job performance reward

a. Staff Maintenance

This is concerned with making the work environment and housing allowances conducive for workers, pertinent practices include; promotion and transfer, motivation, staff safety, security and health services. It is pertinent that educational establishments have sound policies in respect of staff transfer and promotion to ensure that justice and fairness prevail in dealing with staff. As work to be performed in the school is important, the mood of the man to perform the job is equally important. For maximum and productive goal attainment, the school head must ensure the comfort and happiness of the workers. That can be done through prompt payment of salary, and ensuring a safe and healthy working environment.

b. Staff Relations

There must be a good communication network in the school to enable workers to be constantly informed of the progress being made in the school. Workers should be encouraged in planning and decision making process in the school. Workers should be encouraged by recognizing the staff as human beings with feelings, interest, needs and emotions and treating them as such with fairness and respect (Peretomode, 2009).

c. Staff Development

This is the process of appraising staff performances and identifying their key skills and competence that need development or training to improve their skills for better performance. It involves providing development programme and training courses that are suitable for the programme. The success of educational organization hinges on the strength and quality of the staff members. There is need to change through training and to improve and grow in competence. This can be done through in-service training, conference, workshop and seminars

d. Procurement of Staff

Human resource management planning functions start with the process of recruitment and selection by which educational institutions get the best personnel to interpret and implement the curriculum programmes. Staffing of schools is a job performed by the ministry of education through its agencies in the federal and state government. Procurement of staff in education deals with obtaining people with appropriate and necessary skills, abilities, knowledge and experience to fill the vacant teaching posts in schools.

e. Job Performance Reward

This involves the design and administration of rewards for jobs performed. It is very important that management, ministry of education and its agencies take the issue of reward system very seriously. Staff performance would increase substantially if they are adequately compensated according to the quality and quantity of work done.

Facility Planning

Facilities are important tools that generate output in any functioning organization. It is the brain of an organization. Taking a cursory look at the school system, school plants precipitate the realization of educational goals as stated by Federal Republic of Nigeria (2001) as the building of a free and democratic society a just and egalitarian society a united, strong and self-reliant nation, a great and dynamic economy, a land full of bright opportunities for all citizens. Therefore, we cannot override questions on school facilities management to attain the stated educational goals which is been considered here as quality education attainment.

School facility is the haul mark of all the kings employed by the members of the school communities towards the attainment of the goals and objectives of the school. It is the resources put to use by the human elements in the school to make for functional and quality educational delivery process. In line with the concept of school facility, Kaegon (2011) posited that school facility could be used interchangeably with school plants. Plants are various areas that make up the school like materials and teaching facilities. School plant and facilities induce positive teaching/learning outcomes. Obasi and Asodike (2012) reiterated that school plant universally entails the whole school structures materials resources as well as the overall school locations including other fixtures both mobile and immobile ones that promotes teaching learning effectiveness. In congruence with the above view point, Asiabaka (2009) acknowledged that learning takes place in a particular location not on the air. The scholar further explained that students need good learning environment with sufficient cross ventilation so as to grapple with learning challenges. Continuing the scholar added that facilities are necessary tools for academic excellence and are therefore inevitable.

While contributing to the same view Mandah (2006) contended that the importance of learning resources cannot be over-emphasized and went further to enlist them to include administrative offices, laboratories for different subjects that require them, libraries etc.

On the other hand, Agabi (2005) grouped school plants into the purpose for which they serve and as such categorized them into four groups thus;

- (i) Basic instructional materials
- (ii) Recreational resources
- (iii) Inhabited resources
- (iv) General - purpose materials

Basic instructional materials are those used' by the teacher in the course of teaching /earning interactions.

School Funding and Human Resources Planning for Business Education Teachers

School funding may be done through the federal, state and local government.

It is always easy to quantify material inputs. A government may wish to pursue a policy of equalization of inputs in schools. In such cases, quantifiable inputs like buildings, qualification of teachers, pupil-teacher ratios, class-size and expenditure per pupil should be properly determined by the government which ensures the even distribution of resources to schools.

Social justice demands that all schools be given the same treatment. In this regard however, let us have a glance at the disparities between the urban and rural schools in terms of their educational facilities. With regard to almost every conceivable social amenity, the urban areas fare better than the rural areas. This disparity is especially apparent in the area of educational facilities.

This situation holds true in virtually all countries, but it is more exaggerated in developing countries where a wide gap exists between the educational levels of urban and rural dwellers. It is not surprising therefore to find that the schools in urban areas are better constructed, better maintained and better furnished. This is not to say however that public schools in urban areas are in good shape (Ololube, 2009). Far from it, many urban schools are in a terrible state of disrepair and lack even in basic facilities. Although this is so, in relation to rural schools, urban schools are generally better maintained and equipped. The reasons for this are not far-fetched. The towns have concentrations of population, which often seem politically more articulate than their rural counterparts. Education and maintenance policy makers are more sensitive to such areas. In addition, offices for the administration of schools are invariably in urban areas so the factor of proximity accounts partly for the observed disparity. Ogbodo (1995) says children of senior government and education officials attend schools in urban areas so these officials are likely to be more intimately acquainted with the physical state of the urban schools than the rural schools. It is important that government policies with regard to maintenance should be aimed at removing this disparity (Ogbodo, 1995).

The policy of equalization of inputs may be pursued through the equalization of tax bases to enable schools in poor local government areas to have enhanced tax bases. Another device would be to use equalization of per pupil or per capita expenditure services. A third option may be to equalize physical inputs like books, materials and non-academic staff. Apart from the equalization goal, some measure of equity is desirable; equity is more than equality. Though it is abstract and less liable to quantification, it encompasses justice, equality, humanity, morality and right.

The success or failure of the education industry to attract enough government revenue may be conditioned by several factors. One such factor is the rate of growth of the national economy. Should economic growth for instance, lag behind the demand for education, the annual increments to educational budget are likely to decrease leaving little or no room for expansion. Another factor that plays a role is the condition of world market as most third world countries depend on it for the sale of mineral oil and agricultural products. Competition from other sectors of the economy and local politics among competing political parties are also factors to consider (Ololube, 2013).

In Nigeria, education funding is the responsibility of the federal, state and local government levels. The funds are provided for approximately 45,020 primary, 6,100 secondary schools and about 159 Universities, 100 colleges of education and polytechnics. The private sector establishes about 11,000 nurseries, 5,600 primary and 800 secondary schools throughout the country. There is a discrepancy in funding contributions between federal, state and local governments as stated in the concurrent list of the constitution. For example, Rivers State alone houses approximately 245 public secondary schools and provides funding for them (Ministry of Education, 2011). The differences between the public schools and the private schools are very glaring. The private schools are supposed to be complimenting the public schools; instead, they are often seen as rivals because most of the private schools are better equipped than the public ones.

Challenges Faced in Human Resource Management Planning of Business Education Teachers in the 21st Century

As indispensable as human resources planning in the 21st century Education, geared towards development, there exist some frustrating factors that undermine the planning and the execution processes, they are:

Poor Funding/Allocation and Distribution: This is a major factor to the human resource management planning. It is very alarming to witness diversion of funds meant for human resource planning as well as the execution. The planning of education cannot progress to achieve what it is meant to achieve without the effective utilization of funds. Despite the budget for education in Nigeria, it is still underfunded. Most times, the administrative officers create a lot of bureaucracies in the educational system that will enable them to siphon the released fund in to their ever-swallowing bank accounts. According to Egbule and Igbogi (2004) in Ezeugwa (2006) disbursement of funds is a task through which the financial resources of a school are distributed to various areas of educational programmes. The different programmes outlined to bring about change in education, require the effective application of fund. But where these funds are massaged into the pockets of the administrators, the plans for education cannot succeed at all. All the regimes in Nigeria do witness massive diversion of funds meant for the development of education and consequently, the economy. Hence, the economy cannot develop if education is not developed. It was not doubtful when Ogbonnaya (2005) asserted that during Obasanjo's regime, funds meant for education were diverted to some other projects from where they were bagged by corruption-infected politicians.

In a school system, it is the responsibility of the Principal to ensure that budgeted funds are appropriately allocated to the relevant areas of needs in a manner that will enhance the achievement of school objectives. Ndu in Ezeugwa (2006) stressed that favoritism, embezzlement of funds provided for some projects and relationship have brought about under-utilization of human resources in the educational system, reasons being that some Principals or administrators divert funds to areas that were not originally budgeted for just to make personal gains. It therefore becomes crystal clear to state if the economy of Nigeria must develop, the funds meant for education must be allocated and equitably distributed.

Lack of Reliable Data: Nigeria has an estimated population of hundred million people during the last census, which was also influenced and manipulated. The increase in population will definitely lead to increase in student enrolment, increase in the number of facilities and equipment (Ogbonnaya, 2005). But a major challenge is that the data available are really falsified; this is why you have highly unutilized facilities in some part of the country and in some areas they have no facility to use at all. The educational planners become frustrated in trying to get accurate data of various schools. Even when they work with the existing manipulated data, their efforts seem to be futile. The financial implication of the astronomical increase in enrollment is one of the most dreaded consequences of the social demand approach to education in all levels. No one can possibly know in any appreciable detail how the future will look like without necessary sufficient data before projecting into the future. Most times, the educational planners do not have the accurate population data to work with.

It is quite interesting to note that educational institutions at all levels are busy increasing the students' enrollments and academic programmes without matching it with the corresponding academic and non-academic staff to attend to them. The shortage of human resource will surely present a major setback to the educational goals. The increase in the drop-out rates, and repeaters rates are caused by inadequate academic staff to teach the students. Most often, the teachers are not qualified for the courses they are teaching and sometimes, the available human resources are over-utilized or under-utilized due to inaccurate data to show the extent of their availability and utilization.

Administrative Constraints: There are absence of clear administrative polices as to the quality and quantity of staff, staff welfare and system of promotion, the administrative structure and schedule of duties. Ebong (2006) pointed out that “the adequacy of school facility is measured by the extent to which it satisfies the requirements of the school programme. For instance, most often staffing and promotion are not based on civil service procedures as the managers have other instructions outside the civil service procedures on who to employ or promote as the case may be which tends to affect the psychological state of some personnel thereby making them to utilize less of their best in the school.

Political and Policy Constraints: There are varieties of influences and pressures from within and outside the educational institution. The educational institution has failed to distinguish between the political and the technical aspects of educational decisions which constitute a significant constraint. In a situation where the President or the Governor of the federation or a State respectively appoints a Minister or Commissioner of Education who does not know anything about education, invariably, these unprofessional appointees would not have what it takes to harness the resources in educational sector to produce quality output. Oni (2000) stated that there is constraint of underdevelopment of human resources with the critical skills, which have resulted to a substantial negative impact on productivity, managerial effectiveness, firm operations and output. Nwafor (2012) in his study demonstrated the extent to which the use of resource allocation power can affect the performance of the education system. For example, the policy of admitting students based on quota system is a human resource management constraint to education. In a situation where the admission procedure into the universities and unity schools are mostly based on community list, politician’s list, vice chancellors’ list and so on and no longer on merits is a problem to the achievement of educational goals and objectives.

Poor Working Condition: It is not out of way if staff expects to be paid finance rewards commensurate with the services performed. The ideal thing is to have a systematic producer for establishing a sound reward system and structure. A good remuneration tends to reduce inequalities between staff earnings, raise their individual morale, motivate them to work for pay increase and promotions, reduces inter group friction and employee grievances. Teachers’ salaries are not paid alongside with other civil servants and in some cases, teachers are owned many months of salary areas.

As the 21st century world is undergoing rapid changes, there is urgency for few educational needs such as the call for use of ICT in business education. Current call for ICT business usage in education is worthy but, its implementation in the nation is in the toddling stage. Nwufo (2009), evidently noted that ICT penetration and usage remains very low and so the need to train many teachers at all levels in ICT to equip them for re-engineering the society through the skills (Oni, 2009); ICT provides the most expensive means of rapid dissemination of information and imparting knowledge, decentralization of work, expansion of work force and with ICT, the teacher becomes a facilitator, supervisor and a guide for classroom instruction. However, compulsory acquisition of ICT skill by teachers should be given priority attention despite the fact that most teachers cannot buy the computer set or laptop because of poor salary. Other challenges of human resource management planning that have direct effect on the achievement of our predetermined educational objectives in this 21st century include;

- i. High rate of students and staff indiscipline

- ii. Funding issues
- iii. Poor recruitment process
- iv. Little or no induction of human resources
- v. Poor supervision/appraisal of staff
- vi. Poor personnel commitment to work and
- vii. Incessant transfer of teachers

Conclusion

Human Resource Management Planning is very vital in the 21st century business education system, this is due to its strategic role and operational roles being carried out in the educational sector. It dealt appropriately with the aspect of staff maintenance, staff relations, staff development, procurement of staff and staff performance reward. The study therefore concludes that human resource management planning in this 21st century remains a veritable means of ensuring the success of education sector in meeting the needs and aspiration of the students and the society at large, and, enhance nation building in Nigeria. As such, whatever needs to be done in the education sector to improve the quality of its human resource should be done in all sincerity and with every urgency for education to fully achieve its predetermined educational goals and objectives.

Suggestions

Considering the importance of human resource management planning in the 21st century education in Nigeria, the following suggestions were made.

1. The educational sector should be provided with reliable data to enhance their planning in achieving development in Nigeria.
2. Computer literacy should be incorporated (Practical Aspect) into the schools' curriculum in Nigeria for better productivity.
3. The Government should make available funds for educational sector needed for its effective planning and consequent executions of its plans, hence no society can develop more than her educational development.
4. The working of educational personnel across the country should be reviewed and improved. Only this will energize them to put their best as well as being retained in teaching profession.
5. Standard of education in Nigeria should be up dated to meet the rapid social changes in our present day Nigeria society.
6. All levels of human resources in the educational sector in Nigeria should be trained to acquire ICT competencies. This will help the staff to meet up with the changes in this technological world.

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